
Curriculum Development Model of Islamic Education Based On the MB-KM Program

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ABSTRACT: The study aims to develop an Islamic Education curriculum model based on the MB-KM program at Al-Hilal College Sigli, using the ADDIE model of Research and Development (R&D). The analysis stage involves curriculum needs identification, learning objectives analysis, student characteristics assessment, MB-KM program evaluation, literature review, and field studies. The design stage establishes learning objectives, flexible curriculum structure, material organization, learning and assessment methods, integration of Islamic values and MB-KM principles, and creation of modules. The development stage validates the design through expert assessment. Data is collected through interviews, observation, documentation, and questionnaires, and analyzed descriptively, qualitatively, and quantitatively. The findings indicate the curriculum aligns with MB-KM principles like interdisciplinary learning, digital technology, collaborative learning, flexibility, and activity assessment while adhering to relevant standards and industry needs. The curriculum is rated "Feasible" by expert validators, with an average score close to "Very Feasible".

KEYWORDS: Curriculum Development Model, Islamic Education, MB-KM Program

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the times and the increasingly dynamic demands of society require educational institutions, especially higher education, to be able to adapt the curriculum and learning systems implemented. This is in line with the curriculum development theory put forward by (Qolbi et al., 2021), which states that the curriculum must always be adapted to the needs and changes of society. Educational institutions must be able to prepare students to face challenges and opportunities in the future.

Curriculum in educational institutions must always be developed because it is curriculum as subject matter, which means that the curriculum is a series of content for the learning process so that the materials prepared by lecturers are delivered to students (Nofrizal et al., 2022). In this case the curriculum is structured into various specific subjects or in other forms of curriculum development. The main problem often faced in the curriculum development process is the absence of a definite method for formulating good outcomes and considering graduate learning outcomes (CPL), course learning outcomes (CPMK), and indicators of learning success (Dzikria et al., 2021). Additionally, one of the main challenges in implementing the MB-KM curriculum is administrative problems in building collaboration between universities and external partners, both among universities, schools, and industry (Suastika et al., 2022). The imbalance in human resources and facilities between universities is also a factor that causes this policy to not work optimally; for example, internet access is not yet available evenly throughout Indonesia. Furthermore, the administrative handling of students who take cross-study or cross-campus courses needs to be considered to avoid causing new problems (Muhajir et al., 2021).

There is an interesting phenomenon in the context of curriculum development. In other words, the new ministry policy that must be implemented by the University is the Program MB-KM which is regulated in Minister of Education regulations No.3 No.3. 2020. Related to national higher education standards, namely the right to study outside the curriculum for three semesters (Mariati, 2021). In a period of six (6) years, Higher Education Standards (SN-Dikti and now the term has changed to SNPT) have changed three (3) times, namely; 1) Minister of Research, Technology and Higher Education Regulation Number 49 of 2014, 2) Minister of Research, Technology and Higher Education Regulation Number 44 of 2015, and 3) Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 3 of 2020. Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 3 of 2020 coincides with the MB-KM policy (Suastika, et al., 2022).

The MB-KM launched by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia is an effort to provide flexibility and independence to universities in managing the curriculum and learning systems (Rohman et al., 2022). Curriculum development theory by (Handayani et al., 2020) emphasizes the importance of involving various stakeholders in the curriculum development process, including educators, practitioners and the community. The MB-KM program provides space for universities to collaborate with various parties in curriculum development. MB-KM is expected to address the challenges faced by universities in producing graduates aligned with current advancements in science and technology, the needs of the business and industrial sectors, and the evolving dynamics of society (Intan et al., 2023). MB-KM offers students the chance to spend one semester or earn 20 credits by exploring subjects beyond

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their current study program within the same university. Additionally, students can opt for a maximum of two semesters or 40 credits to study within their current program at other universities, explore different programs at various universities, or engage in learning experiences outside the university (Lubis et al., 2024).

Al-Hilal Sigli Islamic College of Science as an Islamic higher education institution needs to develop an Islamic Education curriculum that is in line with the MB-KM program. This aims to produce graduates who not only have academic competence, but also practical competence and are relevant to the needs of industry and society. Curriculum development theory by Robin Fogarty emphasizes the importance of learning objectives, learning experiences, and evaluation in curriculum development (Fogarty et al., 2009).

Based on initial observations on the Islamic education Curriculum at the Al-Hilal Sigli Islamic Science College, they are designing an MB-KM-based Islamic education curriculum, but there are several obstacles in integrating the Islamic education curriculum with MB-KM, such as teaching assistance which has not been prepared well because it is a new program and has not been socialized. Well. However, on the other hand, the right to receive recognition for conversion of 20 credits is also not yet visible in the course specifications recognized in teaching assistantships. For this reason, the Islamic education Study Program must immediately facilitate this with various measurable guidelines and mechanisms. The implementation of one semester of learning activities outside the study program at the same university is based on the closeness of the CPL formulation of the study program within the scientific group, which has not been implemented well because the courses that students are allowed to take have not been regulated according to the applicable guidelines and regulations.

From the several problems above, it is clear that the Islamic Education curriculum needs to be designed well, so that it can provide a model for the formation of an MB-KM-based Islamic education curriculum. Therefore, the researcher intends to conduct research related to the MB-KM-based Islamic education curriculum development model at Al-Hilal Sigli Islamic Science College. In this case the researcher focuses on the Islamic Education Study Program.

METHOD

Research approach

This research is included in development research known as Research and Development (R&D), which is a qualitative approach (Muhammad Iqbal, et al., 2021). According to Borg and Gall in (Setyosari, 2012), development research is a method employed to create and support the production of research items. It is utilized in studies directed towards both product creation and assessing the product's efficacy (Sugiyono, 2014). According to (He, 2024) educational research and development (R&D) is a systematic approach utilized to create and verify educational materials and practices. The model that corresponds to the final results in this research is the ADDIE model with the final result being a model product or guidance manual. (Fayuan Mai, et al., 2024). However, this research was carried out using ADDIE which was limited to step 3 only.

Borg and Gall's explanation illustrates that the stages of R&D can be constrained, therefore, in this study, the ADDIE model is restricted to only step 3. This is due to the fact that conducting extensive R&D requires a significant amount of funding, a lengthy duration, and originality. Limitations on time and research execution up to step 3 are adequate for evaluating the validity and practicality of the model under development (Gall, 1983). The following are the steps involved in this development research, as explained above:

Figure 1 Development Flowchart

Analysis

The initial step in the ADDIE model is to analyze users' needs (Tjahyadi, et al., 2023). The analysis stage in developing the Islamic Education curriculum based on the MB-KM program at the Al-Hilal Sigli Islamic College of Science is a very important starting point in comprehensively understanding the needs, goals and context that will form the basis for development of an effective and relevant

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curriculum. At this stage, a holistic and thorough approach will be applied to ensure that every important aspect is carefully considered such as identification of curriculum needs, analysis of learning objectives, student characteristics and educational context, evaluation of the MB-KM program, literature review and field studies.

Design

The design stage is a phase that allows curriculum developers to describe in detail how the structure, content, learning methods and assessments will be structured in the Islamic Education curriculum based on the Independent Learning Campus program at Al-Hilal Sigli Islamic College of Science. The steps at this design stage will take into account educational needs, goals and context and will produce a comprehensive framework for the learning process.

Development

The development stage is a very important process in turning design plans into concrete learning materials that are ready to be used. At this stage, the development team will design, develop and arrange in detail all curriculum components, including learning modules, teaching materials and other learning resources. Careful detail and a systematic approach will ensure that the resulting learning materials are of high quality and relevant to the stated learning objectives.

This model design was validated by curriculum expert and Lecture of Islamic Education. Validation was carried out by curriculum experts, using a questionnaire that had been prepared. This design validation activity can be carried out in a discussion forum where researchers first present their product design and its advantages. Based on the completed validation activities, information on product weaknesses and strengths will be obtained which will be used as improvement material at the design revision stage.

Table 2 Achievement Levels and Data Qualifications

81-100 %	Very good	Very decent, no need for revision
61-80 %	Good	Decent, no need for revision
41-60%	Enough	Inadequate needs to be revised
21-40 %	Not enough	Not suitable, needs to be revised
<20 %	Very little	Very inappropriate, needs to be revised

Data collection technique

Research has a main objective, namely to obtain data. In order to collect the required data, data collection techniques are needed. This step is very strategic so that researchers are able to obtain data that meets the required standards. This research uses four types of data collection methods: (a) interviews (interviews); (b) questionnaires; (c) observation; and (d) documentation (Amirzan, et al., 2021).

Data analysis technique

After data is collected through interviews, questionnaires and data documentation, it needs to be analyzed. The analysis technique used to analyze research data is descriptive qualitative. This data analysis technique is used to analyze data collected at the validation stage. Correct and valid data analysis results show that the instruments used by researchers are also valid. Validation is intended to test the feasibility of the Islamic education curriculum being developed and its conformity to MB-KM. The data analysis technique used is quantitative descriptive analysis. The designed product which is then implemented is carried out by a feasibility test using instruments according to the Likert scale (Sugiyono, 2014). The Likert scale feasibility test uses four options, namely disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree. The data obtained is in the form of assessment score grades, namely 1, 2, 3, 4. After the data is obtained, then the assessment score conversion is carried out which can be categorized as shown in table 4 as follows: (Sudjana, 2016).

Table 3 Assessment Categories

Average Answer Score	Category
$Mi + 1,5 Sdi < X \leq Mi + 3 Sdi$	Very Worth It
$Mi < X \leq Mi + 1,5 Sdi$	Worthy
$Mi - 1,5 Sdi < X \leq Mi$	Not Worth It
$Mi - 3 Sdi < X \leq Mi - 1,5 Sdi$	Not feasible

The ideal average value (Mi) and deviation (Sdi) are obtained using the formula as in Figure 2 below.

$$Mi = \frac{1}{2} (\text{highest score} + \text{lowest score})$$

$$Sdi = \frac{1}{6} (\text{highest score} - \text{lowest score})$$

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RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Curriculum Analysis of Islamic education STIT Al Hilal Sigli

The researcher conducted an initial observation to explore the potential and problems of implementing the (MB-KM) program at the Islamic Education Study Program at STIT Al-Hilal Sigli. Data was collected by referring to the existing curriculum to identify courses that could be developed into an MB-KM based curriculum. The curriculum development focused on components like objectives, materials, methods, and evaluation. It aimed to produce graduates with relevant competencies for modern community needs, such as leadership, entrepreneurship, digital literacy, and adaptability. The development followed principles of relevance, flexibility, and continuity based on socio-cultural values, student development, science/technology progress, and stakeholder inputs. Methods included lectures, discussions, projects, simulations, online/offline learning, teaching programs, and community service. Evaluations covered knowledge mastery, attitudes, behavior, and skills through exams, projects, portfolios, teaching practices, and partner assessments. The MB-KM curriculum tailored to stakeholder needs aims to produce quality Islamic education graduates ready for modern challenges and opportunities.

Curriculum Design for Islamic Education Based on MB-KM Program

The implementation of MB-KM is essentially based on the curriculum design formed by the Islamic Education study program. Therefore, MB-KM based on the Islamic education study program is often found in Islamic higher education institutions. At STIT AL-Hilal, the MB-KM Islamic education curriculum design has not been prepared in accordance with the basic principles of MB-KM implementation. Therefore, the researchers and the STIT AL-Hilal Sigli curriculum development team designed using an integrated model, namely: 86 credits are taught in semesters 1-4 in the form of classroom lectures within the study program itself and in accordance with the disciplines of Islamic education and its foundations. While in semesters 5-6, 20 credits of lectures are studied outside the university, namely teaching assistance and thematic community service programs (KKN), and even the writing of the thesis can be started as early as the beginning of semester 7. This enabled students to complete their studies in only seven semesters.

The implementation of field lectures for 2 semesters or the equivalent of 38 credits in MB-KM, according to the Head of the Study Program, "is an effort to create competent graduates who can solve complex problems, think critically, creatively, have human management skills, be able to coordinate with others, have emotional intelligence, the ability to assess and make decisions, a service-oriented orientation, negotiation skills, and cognitive flexibility as well as competitiveness ready to face the new normal era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0."

The MB-KM curriculum at STIT AL Hilal Sigli consists of 146 credits, which allows it to be completed in only 8 semesters. This may be an addition of 6 credits from the minimum requirement set by the Directorate of Higher Education, which is only 140 credits (Directorate General of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture, 2020). The Islamic education study program offers two models of Expertise Fields (BKP), namely teaching assistance/campus teaching in Semester 5 and the Thematic Community Service Program (KKN) Teaching in the Village in Semester 6. As for semesters 1-4, students took the same curriculum as the regular curriculum.

The following is a list of courses offered in the teaching assistance program and the Thematic Community Service Program (KKN-T) Teaching in the Village:

Table 4 Conversion of Semester V Courses with the Teaching Assistance

NO	COURSE CODE	COURSE	CREDITS
1	PAI 307	Educational Management and Supervision	2
2	PAI 308	Learning Strategies	2
3	PAI 608	Practice Of Orientation on Madrasah Introduction (POPM)	2
4	PAI 606	Curriculum Development	2
5	PAI 602	Micro Teaching Islamic education	2
7	PAI 406	Design Of Media and Learning Resources for Islamic education	2
8	TAR 701	Teaching Practice	4
9	PAI 510	Islamic education Learning Planning II	2
10	PAI 503	Islamic education Learning Evaluation	2
TOTAL			20

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Table 5 Conversion of Semester VI Courses with the Thematic KKN Teaching

NO	COURSE CODE	COURSE	CREDITS
1	PAI 801	Community Service Program	4
2	PAI 410	Practice of Worship	2
3	OPS 311	Entrepreneurship	2
4	PAI 309	Tajwid II	2
5	PAI 402	Sociology of Education	2
7	PAI 509	Qiratul Kutub II	2
8	OPS 112	Islamic Religious Culture and Civilization	2
9	STI 205	Morality and Sufism	2
TOTAL			18

Based on the classification of courses presented by the researcher above, the model of curriculum development design for the Islamic education Study Program based on MB-KM is as follows:

Figure 2. Curriculum Development Design of Islamic education Study Program Based on MB-KM

From the figure above, it can be seen that in semester 5, students can participate in MB-KM activities in the Teaching Assistance or Campus Teaching program of their choice, then in semester 6 students can choose the Thematic KKN program. The study program and academics will then convert it into appropriate courses.

Development of Islamic education Curriculum based on MB-KM

In the development, the researcher used Fogarty's integrated model theory, which is integrated with the Legal Basis, National and Institutional Policies for Higher Education Curriculum Development. To realize curriculum development in the Islamic Education study program, integration with MB-KM is carried out through procedures and steps: Determining Graduate Profiles, Determining Learning Outcomes (CP), Forming Courses and Semester Credit System (SKS), Forming Courses, Feasibility and Needs Study, and Preparation of the Initial Concept of Curriculum Planning.

Furthermore, the results of the MB-KM curriculum development in the Islamic education Study Program at STIT Al-Hilal Sigli are presented in a table that includes the course code, course, number of credits, compulsory/elective status, and information related to the implementation of MB-KM in each course.

Table 6. Results of Development with STIT AL-Hilal Sigli

NO	COURSE CODE	COURSE	CREDITS	COMPULSORY	LEARNING PROGRAM
1	STI 101	PANCASILA	2	National	
2	STI 102	INDONESIAN LANGUAGE	2	National	
3	STI 103	ARABIC LANGUAGE 1	2	Study Program	

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4	STI 104	ISLAMIC STUDIES METHODOLOGY	2	Study Program	Within the Study Program	
5	STI 105	ENGLISH 1	2	Study Program		
6	STI 106	FIQH 1	2	Study Program		
7	STI 107	ULUMUL QUR'AN 1	2	Study Program		
8	STI 108	ULUMUL HADIST 1	2	Study Program		
9	STI 109	HISTORY OF ISLAMIC CIVILIZATION	2	Study Program		
10	STI 110	KALAM SCIENCE	2	Study Program		
11	OPS 111	BASIC NATURAL SCIENCE	2	Study Program		
12	OPS 112	BASIC SOCIAL AND CULTURAL SCIENCES	2	Study Program		
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER I			24			
1	STI 201	CIVIC EDUCATION	2	National		Within the Study Program
2	STI 202	ARABIC LANGUAGE II	2	Study Program		
3	STI 203	ENGLISH II	2	Study Program		
4	STI 204	BASIC MATHEMATIC	2	Study Program		
5	STI 206	USHUL FIQH I	2	Study Program		
6	TAR 207	TAJWID 1	2	Study Program		
7	TAR 208	EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE I	2	Study Program		
8	PAI 209	FIQH II	2	Study Program		
9	PAI 210	COUNSELING GUIDANCE	2	Study Program		
10	OPS 211	ARABIC-MALAY WRITING	2	Study Program		
11	TAR 601	EDUCATIONAL STATISTICS	2	Study Program		
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER II			22			
1	STI 301	GENERAL PHILOSOPHY	2	Study Program	Within the Study Program	
2	STI 302	INTERPRETATION (TAFSIR)	2	Study Program		
3	STI 303	HADITH	2	Study Program		
4	TAR 304	PHILOSOPHY OF EDUCATION	2	Study Program		
5	TAR 305	EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY	2	Study Program		
6	PAI 306	USHUL FIQH II	2	Study Program		
7	PAI 307	FUNDAMENTALS OF THE CURRICULUM	2	Study Program		
8	STI 401	ANTI-CORRUPTION EDUCATION	2	Study Program		
9	PAI 310	TARIKH TASYRIK	2	Study Program		
10	PAI 511	ISLAMIC EDUCATION SPECIAL METHODS	2	Study Program		
11	PAI 504	FIQH LEARNING	2	Study Program		
12	PAI 404	QIRATUL POLE I	2	Study Program		

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TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER III			24		
1	PAI 403	DEVELOPMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION	2	Study Program	Within the Study Program
2	PAI 606	CURRICULUM DEVELOPMENT	2	Study Program	
3	PAI 405	ISLAMIC EDUCATION LEARNING PLANNING I	2	Study Program	
4	PAI 407	EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE II	2	Study Program	
5	PAI 408	ISLAMIC EDUCATION HADIST I	2	Study Program	
6	PAI 409	INTERPRETATION OF PAI I	2	Study Program	
7	PAI 309	TAJWID II	2	Study Program	
8	PAI 509	QIRATUL POLE II	2	Study Program	
9	PAI 508	QAWAID FIQHIYAH	2	Study Program	
10	PAI 507	MASAIL FIQHIYAH	2	Study Program	
11	PAI 603	LEARNING THE HISTORY OF ISLAMIC CULTURE	2	Study Program	
12	PAI 607	FIQH MUQARRAN	2	Study Program	
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER IV			24		
1	PAI 501	EDUCATION MANAGEMENT AND SUPERVISION	2	Study Program	Outside the Study Program (Teaching Assistance)
2	PAI 308	LEARNING STRATEGIES	2	Study Program	
3	PAI 608	PRACTICE INTRODUCTION TO MADRASAH ORIENTATION (POPM)	2	Study Program	
4	PAI 605	LEARNING AQIDAH AKHLAK	2	Study Program	
5	PAI 602	MICRO TEACHING PAI	2	Study Program	
6	PAI 406	ISLAMIC EDUCATION MEDIA DESIGN AND LEARNING RESOURCES	2	Study Program	
7	TAR 701	FIELD EXPERIENCE PRACTICE	4	Study Program	
8	PAI 510	ISLAMIC EDUCATION LEARNING PLANNING II	2	Study Program	
9	PAI 503	ISLAMIC EDUCATION LEARNING EVALUATION	2	Study Program	
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER V			20		
1	PAI 801	COMMUNITY SERVICE PROGRAM	4	Study Program	
2	PAI 410	PRACTICE OF WORSHIP	2	Study Program	
3	OPS 311	ENTREPRENEURSHIP	2	National	
4	PAI 309	TAJWID II	2	Study Program	

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5	PAI 402	SOCIOLOGY OF EDUCATION	2	Study Program	Outside the Study Program (KKN T)
6	PAI 509	QIRATUL KUTUB II	2	Study Program	
7	OPS 112	ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS CULTURE AND CIVILIZATION	2	Study Program	
8	STI 205	MORALITY AND SUFISM	2	Study Program	
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER VI			18		
1	STIT 703	TRANSLATION STUDIES	2	Study Program	Within the Study Program
2	PAI 704	ISLAMIC EDUCATION SEMINAR	2	Study Program	
3	PAI 705	PHILOSOPHY OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION	2	Study Program	
4	PAI 701	ISLAMIC LEADERSHIP	2	Study Program	
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER VII			8		
1	STI 802	SCRIPT	6	Study Program	Within the Study Program
TOTAL CREDITS SEMESTER VIII			6		

The results of the validation of the MB-KM-based Islamic education Curriculum carried out by four validators, namely the Islamic education Curriculum Expert, MB-KM Curriculum Expert, Head of quality assurance agency, and Islamic education Lecturers, can be seen in the following table:

Table 7 Results of Validation of the MB-KM based PAI Curriculum

No	Statement	Validator/Score	Category
1	The curriculum has accommodated the MB-KM program by providing slots or credit weights for off-campus activities	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 4	Very Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 4	Very Feasible
2	There are courses that can be taken outside the study program or at other universities.	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 2	Less Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 2	Less Feasible
3	There are courses or activities that facilitate learning outside the classroom, such as: Teaching Assistance, Research, Entrepreneurial Activities, Independent Study/Independent Projects, KKN-T	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 4	Very Feasible
4	There are courses or activities that facilitate interdisciplinary or cross-study program learning.	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
5	There are courses or activities that facilitate learning using digital technology.	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible

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		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 4	Very Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 4	Very Feasible
6	There are courses or activities that facilitate collaborative learning, such as group work or joint projects	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
7	The curriculum has flexibility that allows students to take courses or activities according to their interests and talents.	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 2	
8	There is a mechanism for assessing or recognizing MB-KM activities carried out by students	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
9	The curriculum has met the national higher education standards and applicable regulations	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
10	The curriculum has considered the needs of the world of work and industries related to the Islamic Education study program	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
11	The curriculum has considered the results of recent studies or research in the field of Islamic education	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 3	Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 3	Feasible
12	The curriculum has involved input from stakeholders such as alumni, Islamic education practitioners, and the community.	Islamic Education Curriculum Expert: 4	Very Feasible
		MB-KM Curriculum Expert: 3	Feasible
		Head of quality assurance: 4	Very Feasible
		Islamic Education Lecturer: 4	Very Feasible

The validation results from the Islamic Education Curriculum Expert show that this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is in the "Very Feasible" category with an average score of 3.42. This indicates that the curriculum has met important aspects in developing an MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum, such as accommodating the MB-KM program by providing credit weights for off-campus activities, facilitating learning outside the classroom, using digital technology, and involving input from stakeholders.

Meanwhile, the validation results from the MB-KM Curriculum Expert show that this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is in the "Feasible" category with an average score of 3.25. This assessment is slightly lower than that of the Islamic

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Education Curriculum Expert, particularly in the aspect of the availability of courses that can be taken outside the study program or at other universities.

From the perspective of the Head of quality assurance agency, this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is also rated as "Feasible" with an average score of 3.17. This assessment is lower than that of the Islamic Education Curriculum Expert and the MB-KM Curriculum Expert, particularly in the aspect of the availability of courses that can be taken outside the study program or at other universities, as well as the curriculum flexibility that allows students to take courses or activities according to their interests and talents.

Lastly, the validation results from the Islamic Education Lecturers show that this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is also in the "Feasible" category with an average score of 3.17. This assessment is the same as that of the Head of quality assurance, where the aspect of the availability of courses that can be taken outside the study program or at other universities and the curriculum flexibility are considered less feasible.

Overall, it can be concluded that this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is rated as "Feasible" by the validators with an average score close to the "Very Feasible" category. However, there are several aspects that need to be improved, such as the availability of courses that can be taken outside the study program or at other universities, as well as the curriculum flexibility to better allow students to take courses or activities according to their interests and talents.

CONCLUSION

The development model of the MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum uses a rational approach with the following steps: (1) Analysis of needs and problems; (2) Formulating institutional goals; (3) Developing curriculum design; (4) Preparing curriculum implementation guidelines; (5) Curriculum implementation; (6) Monitoring and evaluation; and (7) Curriculum revision and improvement.

The curriculum design of the Islamic Education Study Program at STIT Al-Hilal Sigli based on MB-KM uses an integrated model, where in semesters 1-4 students attend classes on campus (96 credits), while semesters 5-6 are carried out off-campus through the Teaching Assistance/Campus Teaching program (semester 5) and Thematic Village Teaching Community Service (semester 6) equivalent to 40 credits.

The developed curriculum has met the principles of MB-KM, such as interdisciplinary learning, utilization of digital technology, collaborative learning, flexibility, and assessment of MB-KM activities. This curriculum is also in accordance with applicable standards and regulations, and takes into account the needs of the world of work and industries related to the Islamic Education study program.

The validation results from the MB-KM Curriculum Expert, Head of quality assurance, and Islamic Education Lecturers show that this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is in the "Feasible" category with average scores of 3.25, 3.17, and 3.17 respectively. Overall, this MB-KM-based Islamic Education curriculum is rated as "Feasible" by the validators with an average score close to the "Very Feasible" category. After going through the stages of initial concept development, planning, validation, and receiving a feasibility assessment from curriculum experts, the MB-KM curriculum for the Islamic Education Study Program at STIT Al-Hilal Sigli is declared feasible to be implemented in learning activities without the need for revision.

This study has several limitations that need to be noted. First, this research only covers the curriculum development stage without involving the implementation and evaluation stages of the curriculum that has been developed. Second, curriculum development was carried out only at one institution, namely STIT Al-Hilal Sigli, so the results of this research may not be generalizable to other higher education institutions. Third, this research only focuses on the Islamic Religious Education study program, so it does not include curriculum development for other study programs.

Based on these limitations, the following are recommendations for further research. First, it is recommended to conduct further research that focuses on the implementation and evaluation of the curriculum that has been developed, as well as examining its impact on the learning process and student learning outcomes. Second, expanding the scope of research by involving other higher education institutions, both regional and national, in order to produce a more comprehensive and generalizable curriculum development model. Third, develop curricula for other study programs outside Islamic Religious Education, so that they can make a wider contribution to curriculum development in various scientific disciplines.

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